

PORTRAIT GENRE AND IMAGE INTERPRETATION IN VISUAL ARTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8008719>

Annotation: This article describes in detail the portrait genre and image interpretation in visual arts, negative events expressed in works of art, Fayyum portraits, the main means of expression in painting.

Key words: fine art, portrait genre, image interpretation, Fayyum portrait, monumental painting, character.

Introduction:

Art is a means of depicting the spiritual values, traditions, culture, and life of any nation. With the help of art, it is possible to change and educate people's worldview, outlook on life, imagination. Art nourishes human spirituality.

We will continue to promote the best works of our creative intellectuals in our country and abroad as a main part of our policy in the spiritual and educational sphere. Special attention is paid to the material and spiritual stimulation of talented young people who are entering the world of culture, art, literature and the press, and to improving their housing conditions.

Literature analysis and methodology:

One of the most complex genres of fine art is the depiction of the human face, and in addition to being a skilled master of shapes, proportions, and colors, the artist must have a good understanding of the human personality, be able to perceive his psychological state, be able to know his feelings, and express his color in a manner appropriate to the situation when the painting is being worked on. requires having qualifications. The reason is that it should express the identity, age, character, and status of the person in the work, even the structure of the body, wealth and poverty.

The place of fine art in particular in educating the young generation is incomparable. Visual arts have the ability to have a strong impact on people's emotions. People try to introduce such beauty into their lives by watching works of visual art, seeing the beauty expressed in them, and by seeing the characters in the works, they try to be like them.

Seeing the negative events and ugly behavior expressed in works of art, they draw certain conclusions from them, and try to stay away from such events. The illustrations are extremely bright and each one is unique. Artists create works with the help of painting tools, and they always use the possibilities of drawing, composition. Therefore, color remains an important means of expression in painting.

The creation of a specific image in connection with the inner spiritual world of a person is considered portrait art. Creating a portrait is a complex process of its own, and it can be a work of art as it reflects all aspects of a person, starting from his anatomical structure to his inner mental and spiritual state, as well as his external appearance. A portrait artist needs to

be able to feel the various movements of people, especially to have the ability to depict the sincerity or fake aspects of a person's face.

Results:

A painting is able to effectively express the complex intelligence and thinking of a person, large and small changes occurring in nature, continuous philosophical ideas and fantastic images. The full range of events, events and manifestations is revealed through genres of different directions. There are several genres of fine art, each with its own importance and audience. Especially the portrait genre is distinguished by the fact that artists often appeal and have a large audience.

portraiture is one of the oldest genres, revealing the external and internal experiences of people with the help of images. Fine art works give us the interpretation of the time, culture, and the psyche of the person depicted in the work. Portraiture is one of the oldest genres. In the city of Fayyum, beautiful wax portraits of painters were found. These works were created in ancient Egypt in the 1st-3rd centuries AD.

Fayyum portraits differ from other styles in that they are vivid lifelike images, and that the form is made using a three-dimensional model of light and shade. When the artist works in the portrait genre, he represents a historical image, an image of a contemporary, or an artistic image in his work. As you observe each image in the portrait, you will learn about it. The artist tries to depict his feelings, inner experiences, psychology in each portrait. Currently, great importance is attached to the wide use of examples of our culture, values, national art, wonderful art examples created by our ancestors and known to the whole world in the education of our youth.

Discussion:

Reflecting the image of our great compatriots, great scientists who lived in the past in works of visual art also imposes responsible tasks on creative people. For this reason, it is necessary to study and analyze them. The formation of new spiritual and ideological trends in Uzbekistan, in turn, effectively affects all areas of modern art, expands the scope of creative research, and accelerates the development of artistic thinking.

The art of portraiture had its heyday during the Renaissance. In this period, the glorification of the human personality as the beginning of the highest innovation was considered universal wealth and heroism in art. During the renaissance, painting, sculpture and graphic types of portraits were highly developed. The image of an active, fearless, brave person who knows his worth has become the main character of this era.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be said that the study of existence on a scientific basis and the efforts to use this knowledge in practice created a new system of portraiture. Now, it was depicted not in an unrealistic space and environment, but in the bosom of nature close to man. Among the characters of monumental paintings, the artist begins to work on his image. This process was further developed in the art of the next period.

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